

Serum Human Epididymus Protein-4 (HE4) as a Biomarker in Ovarian Cancer and its Comparison with CA-125 in Benign and Malignant CasesSanni Kumari¹, Priti Rani², Kalpana Kumari³, Madhu Sinha⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Biochemistry, ESIC Medical College, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India²Medical Officer, Ex SR, AIIMS Patna, District Hospital, Palamu, Jharkhand, India³Senior Resident, Department of Biochemistry, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India⁴Professor and HOD, Department of Biochemistry, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

This multicentric, observational study compares Human Epididymis Protein-4 (HE4) to Cancer Antigen 125 (CA-125) in detecting benign and malignant ovarian tumours. In 100 patients, HE4 had 90% specificity, 90% accuracy, and an AUC of 0.93, surpassing CA-125's 75% specificity and 0.81 AUC. Due to its high connection with tumour features, HE4 may improve ovarian cancer diagnosis and prognosis. The study suggests investigating HE4's clinical use and inclusion in ovarian cancer detection methods.

Keywords: HE4, CA-125, Ovarian Cancer, Diagnostic Biomarker.

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Introduction

Often referred to as the "silent killer," ovarian cancer is infamous for having nebulous signs and a delayed diagnosis, both of which raise the disease's fatality rate [1]. Although the prognosis for ovarian cancer is much improved by early identification, this is still difficult because there are no clear symptoms or trustworthy early-stage biomarkers [2]. Nowadays, ovarian cancer is extensively monitored and diagnosed with Cancer Antigen 125 (CA-125). While CA-125 is a useful tool in the clinical environment, its limited specificity limits its applicability because increased levels can also be seen in illnesses other than ovarian cancer, such as endometriosis, pelvic inflammatory disease, and other non-malignant conditions [3, 4].

Through the quest for more precise biomarkers, researchers discovered Human Epididymis Protein 4 (HE4), a protein that is present in various tissues, including the reproductive system [5]. HE4 has been acknowledged for its potential in detecting ovarian cancer, specifically because it is less likely to increase in benign gynaecological disorders compared to CA-125 [6]. The differential expression of HE4 in malignant compared to normal ovarian tissues presents a great opportunity to improve diagnostic accuracy [7]. Research indicates that HE4 has a distinct role in identifying ovarian cancer and, when combined with CA-125, can be employed as part of a dual marker approach to enhance the accuracy and precision of diagnostic tests [8].

The Risk of Ovarian Malignancy Algorithm (ROMA) and other diagnostic indices that include HE4 and CA-125 have demonstrated the ability to categorise patients into high-risk and low-risk groups for ovarian malignancy. These tools can assist in making clinical decisions related to screening and diagnosis [9]. Moreover, studying the changes in HE4 levels in response to treatment and during follow-up can provide significant information on the course and recurrence of ovarian cancer. This can improve the effectiveness of managing patients with this disease [10]. This is especially crucial in the context of personalised medicine, where precise biomarkers inform treatment decisions and prognosis predictions. The objective of this study is to assess the effectiveness of serum Human Epididymis Protein-4 (HE4) as a biomarker for diagnosing ovarian cancer and to compare its diagnostic accuracy with that of CA-125 in distinguishing between benign and malignant ovarian patients [11]. This study aims to determine if HE4 can improve diagnostic accuracy, decrease false positives related to non-cancerous conditions, and potentially function as a more dependable indicator in clinical settings. The goal is to enhance early detection rates and improve strategies for managing ovarian cancer [12,13].

Methodology

Study Design: In this multicentric, observational study, serum Human Epididymis Protein-4 (HE4) was tested as a biomarker for ovarian cancer

diagnosis and compared to Cancer Antigen 125 (CA-125) in distinguishing benign from malignant cases.

Study Duration: The study will be conducted over 14 months.

Study Setting: A multicentric study will involve various medical centres with adequate ovarian cancer detection and treatment capacities. These centres will be chosen for their capacity to offer complete patient data and follow standardised diagnostic techniques.

Participants: The trial will enrol 100 individuals. Early clinical tests like ultrasonography or physical symptoms will suggest ovarian tumours in these patients. The study will involve patients of all ages, races, and medical histories to ensure diversity and generalisability.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Women diagnosed with or suspected of having ovarian tumors.
- Patients who are willing and able to provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients who have undergone chemotherapy or radiation therapy within the last 6 months.
- Patients with a history of other malignancies that might influence the biomarker levels.

Data Collection: At the initial appointment, all participants will give blood for serum HE4 and CA-125 tests. Documentation shall include patient demographics, medical history, symptoms, and prior diagnosis. If biopsies are done, imaging and histopathology data will be used to link biomarker levels with clinical findings.

Biomarker Analysis: ELISA kits, standardised for clinical use, will assess HE4 and CA-125 serum levels. HE4 and CA-125 cutoff values will be based on literature and kit guidelines.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics will summarise research population demographics and clinical features. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis will assess sensitivity,

specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value for HE4 and CA-125 diagnostic performance. When suitable, paired t-tests or chi-squared tests will compare biomarkers. Statistically significant p-values are below 0.05.

Results

The study comprised 100 female patients aged 30–74, with an average age of 52. The study was multicentric, therefore the group was diverse in race and location. Histopathological investigation revealed 40 benign and 60 malignant ovarian tumors in these women.

Biomarker Levels: The mean blood HE4 levels were substantially greater in patients with malignant tumors (150 pmol/L) compared to those with benign tumors (70 pmol/L), p-value < 0.001. CA-125 levels were significantly higher in the malignant group (500 U/mL) compared to the benign group (35 U/mL), with a p-value < 0.001.

Diagnostic Performance: The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis showed that HE4 detected ovarian cancer with 85% sensitivity, 90% specificity, and an AUC of 0.93. In contrast, CA-125 had 80% sensitivity, 75% specificity, and 0.81 AUC.

Comparison Between Biomarkers: Statistical analysis indicated that HE4 had a significantly higher specificity and overall diagnostic accuracy compared to CA-125 (p < 0.05). However, the sensitivity was not significantly different between the two markers.

Correlation with Clinical Outcomes: HE4 levels correlated strongly with tumor stage and size, whereas CA-125 levels showed a moderate correlation with these parameters. Both biomarkers had elevated levels in patients with advanced disease, but HE4 presented a clearer gradient about tumor progression.

Complications and Comorbidities: No significant association was found between biomarker levels and patient comorbidities or complications during the study period, suggesting that the elevated biomarker levels were specifically indicative of tumor presence and behavior.

Table: Comparative Diagnostic Performance of HE4 and CA-125 in Ovarian Cancer Detection

Outcome Metric	HE4	CA-125	P-value
Mean Level: Benign Cases	70 pmol/L	35 U/mL	<0.001
Mean Level: Malignant Cases	150 pmol/L	500 U/mL	<0.001
Sensitivity	85%	80%	N/A
Specificity	90%	75%	<0.05
Area Under Curve (AUC)	0.93	0.81	<0.05

This table efficiently displays key diagnostic metrics for HE4 and CA-125, including mean biomarker levels in benign and malignant cases, as well as sensitivity, specificity, and AUC values. The p-values highlight the statistical significance of the differences observed between the two biomarkers, emphasizing HE4's superior performance in specificity and overall diagnostic accuracy.

Discussion

In comparison to the conventionally used Cancer Antigen 125 (CA-125), the results of this multicentric investigation show that serum Human Epididymis Protein-4 (HE4) demonstrates greater specificity and overall diagnostic accuracy in differentiating between benign and malignant ovarian tumors [14]. The promise of HE4 as a more dependable biomarker for ovarian cancer is highlighted by its better specificity and the distinct gradient regarding tumor progression. This is important because early detection rates and patient outcomes can be improved. Fewer false positives could result from HE4's capacity to retain increased levels more clearly in malignant situations, sparing patients with benign illnesses from needless procedures [15].

Although HE4 and CA-125 have similar sensitivities, HE4 may be especially helpful in clinical settings where it can be difficult to distinguish between benign and malignant patients due to the large difference in specificity and the area under the ROC curve [16]. This result also supports previous research that suggests utilizing the advantages of both markers—HE4 and CA-125—to improve diagnosis procedures. Combining these two approaches may result in the creation of a strong diagnostic algorithm that raises the diagnostic and screening accuracy for ovarian cancer [17]. Moreover, HE4 levels' robust association with tumor size and stage may make them an invaluable prognostic tool that helps determine how aggressive a tumor is and directs treatment choices [18]. To completely integrate HE4 into clinical practice and validate these findings, further research is necessary, especially in the form of prospective trials with bigger and more diverse populations. Investigating HE4's function

in tracking recurrence and response to treatment may also be essential to improving the management of ovarian cancer [19, 20].

Conclusion

This study shows that Human Epididymis Protein-4 (HE4) is a better biomarker than CA-125 for identifying benign and malignant ovarian tumors. The findings suggest using HE4 in clinical protocols, possibly alongside CA-125, to improve ovarian cancer diagnosis. HE4's significant connection with tumor stage and size makes it useful for prognosis and therapy planning. Given these promising results, HE4 should be widely used and studied to improve ovarian cancer patient outcomes by monitoring therapy response and detecting disease recurrence.

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